
D2.4. Energy Community Projects Map

Version	Date
1.0	26/09/2025

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Project information

Project Number	CINEA - 101215402	Acronym	LIFE24-CET_PUBLINK
Full title	Public Authorities linking Energy Communities into Local Plans and Strategies		
EU Project Officer	Talia BRUN		
Disclaimer	Co-funded by the European Union This Life Project n° 101215402 is co-funded by the European Union.		
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Deliverable information

Deliverable	D2.4	Energy Community Projects Map
Work Package	WP2	Inter-sectoral review to understand and exploit the full potential of the Public authorities in Energy Communities
Related Task	T2.1	Select and engage sister projects and lighthouse Energy Communities

Date of delivery	Contractual	M4	Actual	M4
Status	Version 1.0	Final		
Nature	Report			
Dissemination level	Public			

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Executive summary

This report, *Energy Community Projects Map (Deliverable D2.4)*, presents the initial mapping of energy community initiatives and sister projects under the LIFE_PUBLINK project. It aims to identify relevant projects and lighthouse communities across Europe, supporting PUBLINK's goal of strengthening public authority roles in citizen-led energy transitions, and vice versa. The mapping builds on a CINEA-provided list and has been expanded through partner input and stakeholder interviews. As of Month 4, over 50 sister projects and 30 energy communities have been identified.

Findings show energy communities are emerging across Europe but development is uneven. Countries with strong legislation and support show greater activity, while others lag due to regulatory gaps and administrative barriers.

Common challenges include complex administrative procedures, slow grid connections, and lack of financing. Most communities rely on member contributions and public grants. Solar PV dominates, but heating, renovation, and shared mobility are gaining interest.

This analysis confirms that success requires both citizen initiative and proactive public support. The report highlights good practices that can be replicated. As a living document, it will be updated in April 2026 and at the end of the project, serving as a knowledge base for PUBLINK's policy, training, and replication activities.

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the initial findings of the energy community landscape mapping conducted within the LIFE PUBLINK project. It provides an overview of key initiatives across Europe and in specific national and regional contexts in Spain, Germany and Poland based on direct engagement with project partners, European projects coordinators, energy community organizations, national associations, and existing energy communities.

The objectives and methodology of this report are explained below.

a. Objectives of this Report-Map

According to the Grant Agreement, Deliverable 2.4 is defined as follows: *“Mapping of energy community projects will be supported by an initial list provided by CINEA, including ongoing and past projects under LIFE CET, Horizon, and HE programs. A preliminary result will be available by M4, followed by a more comprehensive analysis by M11, and finally, an updated and expanded mapping by M36, incorporating sister projects that join during the project's duration.”*

While this remains the core framework of the deliverable, the scope of D2.4 has been expanded to reflect the broader objectives of Task 2.1 “Select and engage sister projects and lighthouse Energy Communities”. This task is not limited to mapping projects, but explicitly includes the analysis of existing energy communities and initiatives at European, national, and regional levels—such as the Energy Communities Repository, the “Energía Común” Observatory in Spain—focusing on key PUBLINK themes: the role of public entities, citizen participation, heating and cooling technologies, building renovation, and innovative financing mechanisms.

Given that Task 2.1 spans the entire project duration and involves direct engagement with sister projects and energy communities through desk research, interviews, and bilateral meetings, it generates valuable contextual insights from the outset. Considering the relevance of these early results for subsequent project tasks—particularly in co-design, capacity building, and policy development—it was deemed valuable to include a first synthesis of these insights in this deliverable. This deliverable will therefore not only list projects but also begin to reflect the rich contextual knowledge gathered through Task 2.1, serving as a living repository that will be updated and deepened at M11 and M36.

Therefore, the objective of this report is twofold:

1. To provide a dynamic and evolving mapping of sister projects and energy communities relevant to PUBLINK, based on CINEA's input, consortium knowledge, and direct stakeholder engagement.
2. To capture and present early insights on the contextual, structural, and operational characteristics of energy communities in the target regions, serving as a knowledge base for the project's further development and cross-regional learning.

b. Methodology

This deliverable, developed under Task 2.1 "Select and engage sister projects and lighthouse Energy Communities", builds upon the initial requirement to map energy community projects by integrating a structured and multi-level methodological approach. While the foundation of the mapping relies on the list of projects including ongoing and past initiatives under LIFE CET, Horizon, and Horizon Europe programmes, the methodology extends beyond a simple inventory. It combines desk research, targeted data collection, and direct stakeholder engagement to gather qualitative and contextual insights that inform the project's broader objectives on governance, citizen participation, technological innovation, and financing.

The approach is designed to identify not only which projects and communities exist, but also how they operate, which actors drive them, and what challenges and enablers shape their development. This dual focus—on both project mapping and contextual analysis—ensures that the deliverable serves as a dynamic knowledge base for subsequent tasks, including capacity-building, policy co-design, and replication strategies.

The following sections detail the specific methods applied to map sister projects, analyse lighthouse energy communities, and understand the enabling environments in key regions across Europe.

Lighthouse Energy Communities

The process began identifying potential overlaps in planned activities among WP2 partners, particularly regarding planned interviews. To streamline efforts and ensure consistency, a joint questionnaire was co-developed, integrating key thematic inputs from relevant partners:

- Traza Consultoría (TRA) contributed questions on the distribution, evolution, typology of the energy communities in each region (linked to Task 2.1) and

the role of Local and Regional Authorities (LRAs) in energy communities (linked to Task 2.2);

- Dr. Jakob energy research GmbH & Co. KG (JER) provided inputs on relevant innovative generation, storage and management technologies (aligned with Task 2.3);
- Federation Europeenne De Finances Et Banques Ethiques Et Alternatives (FEBEA) led the design of questions on innovative financing mechanisms and financial instruments (in line with its role in Task 2.4).

This consolidated questionnaire (Annex A) was addressed to umbrella organisations and networks that represent or support multiple energy communities within a given region or country. A targeted list of such entities was compiled (Annex B), and each of them was contacted by different partners in their region to introduce the PUBLINK project and invite collaboration. Respondents were offered the option to complete the questionnaire directly or participate in a structured follow-up interview. A variety of response formats were received, and all inputs have been systematically collected to serve as a foundational knowledge base for subsequent tasks within WP2, and to inform Task 3.1.

To capture first-hand experiences from active energy communities, a separate [Google Form survey](#) was designed and disseminated. This was shared with consortium partners and umbrella organisations, requesting them to identify energy communities meeting the following key criteria:

- Active involvement of Local and Regional Authorities (LRAs);
- Strong citizen participation;
- Implementation of shared heating/cooling systems and/or building renovation activities;
- Use of innovative financing mechanisms.

Responses were collected and are being used to preliminarily map energy communities, applying a filtering process based on the above criteria. An exception has been noted in Poland, where currently identified communities primarily focus on photovoltaic solar energy, with limited examples of heating/cooling or renovation projects. Despite this, Polish cases are included to ensure geographical diversity, while acknowledging the technological scope limitation.

The preliminary mapping will be continuously updated and enriched throughout the project duration, as new cases and sister projects are identified. Following the

analysis of survey responses, targeted interviews will be conducted with key representatives of selected energy communities to gain deeper insights into their development trajectories, governance models, challenges, and success factors. These interviews will feed directly into Task 4.2 “Capacity building for strategic policy making for Energy communities” and broader project learning.

European Related Projects

For the mapping of European sister projects, the consortium started from an initial list of projects mentioned in the proposal and expanded it through contributions from all partners—particularly EREN and IRMiR, who have extensive experience in EU-funded initiatives. The list was further enriched with data provided by CINEA, including projects funded under the same or similar calls. A structured data collection template was developed (details of which are presented in Table 01), covering key project characteristics such as objectives, interest in PUBLINK, contact details and our progress made with the collaboration. Through interviews with project coordinators and partners, new initiatives were identified and added to our initial list, progressively enriching our project mapping. As the list grew longer, a column was added to prioritise the most relevant and useful items for the project.

PUBLINK Sister Projects data collection

Acronym	Title	Call	Main topic	Website	Duration	Goal	Pilots/ Countries	Coordinator	Contact person	Mail	Interest for PUBLINK	Priority	Progress made	Partner contact

Table 01_PUBLINK Sister projects.

Consortium members have proactively reached out to sister projects to establish contact, present PUBLINK, and explore synergies in terms of tools, methodologies, results, and mutual learning opportunities. In addition to identifying and contacting project coordinators, several interviews have already been conducted—particularly with projects funded under the LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM call that are nearing completion. These interviews have provided valuable insights into their outputs, outcomes, and lessons learned, many of which are directly applicable to PUBLINK and can be leveraged to ensure continuity and avoid duplication. Beyond gathering concrete results, these exchanges have helped expand the network of related projects that will continue to operate in parallel with PUBLINK, fostering long-term collaboration opportunities.

As Task 2.1 spans the entire project lifecycle, this deliverable represents a living and evolving repository of energy communities and sister projects, which will be regularly updated and expanded until M36. With the upcoming launch of the new LIFE-CET-2024-ENERCOM projects, the consortium plans to conduct further

meetings and structured interviews to deepen synergies and integrate emerging insights into PUBLINK’s activities.

All collected data—including project mappings, assessments, and curated materials such as existing guides and toolkits—will be compiled into a dedicated repository on the project’s microsite. These resources will be adapted to the specific context and needs of PUBLINK to support the development of training materials for Task 4.2.

2. European Related Projects

a. Grant Agreement Sister Projects

This mapping of European sister projects builds upon the initial set of initiatives identified during the proposal development phase and formally listed in the Grant Agreement. These projects were selected not only for their thematic alignment with PUBLINK’s objectives—particularly in the areas of energy communities, citizen engagement, local energy governance, heating and cooling solutions, and innovative financing—but also for their potential to serve as knowledge partners and sources of transferable practices.

This EU project's mapping is designed to go beyond isolated project outcomes by actively engaging with these initiatives to identify synergies, share methodologies, and co-develop scalable solutions. Rather than replicating efforts, PUBLINK aims to build on, connect with, and up-scale successful approaches by integrating lessons learned, leveraging existing networks, and fostering collaboration across different governance levels and technological domains.

Through structured knowledge exchange—via joint workshops, shared tools, and coordinated dissemination—PUBLINK strengthens the impact of these projects while at the same time contributing new insights from its own pilot actions.

The following table (Table 02) presents the sister projects initially referenced in the Grant Agreement, which form the foundational layer of PUBLINK’s collaborative network.

Project name and description	How PUBLINK builds on/up-scales these projects
<p>H2020 RENAISSANCE: Aim is to deliver a community-driven scalable and replicable approach, to implement new business models and technologies supporting clean production and shared distribution of energy in local communities.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will use study cases prepared by the project and different reports and tools on establishing energy communities in RENAISSANCE pilots, like The “RENERGISE Multi-vector Optimization tool”, to find new energy communities development; the “RENAISSANCE online video game” for attractive stakeholder engagement; and the paper “Designing successful energy communities: A comparison of seven pilots in Europe applying the Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis”. NAPE is part of this team.</p>

<p>H2020 REFORMERS aims to provide a set of solutions enabling to analyse and manage REVs reaching the level of an independent energy supply for different highly integrated energy vectors. Most of the innovations we propose combine and integrate existing technologies (generation, storage, distribution) in novel combinations and more integrated architecture, driven by novel algorithms.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will use project experience in the participation of the local industry and other stakeholders in the value chain, including citizens and Energy Communities there, within this scope the REFORMERS project focuses on co-developed arrangements among stakeholder groups, representing the quadruple helix ecosystems (science, policy, industry, society). As the project started in 2023 further the results that could be used in PUBLINK will be analysed during the project implementation. NAPE is a part of the REFORMERS project team.</p>
<p>SCCALE203050: Aim is to scale the growth of energy communities across Europe in the areas of energy efficiency, renewable energy production, district heating and more in households and non-residential buildings.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will use the different guides produced by this project to complement its knowledge in setting up energy communities. These guides will be very useful as a basis for PUBLINK’s community support workshops and we will adapt them to our local contexts and languages for the workshops. Guide: IT-Tools for energy communities.</p>
<p>H2020 LIGHTNESS aims to engage citizens to generate, share and sell renewable energy by supporting the creation of Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) in five European countries, through the development of social engagement, low-cost technologies, regulatory roadmaps, and innovative business models.</p>	<p>PUBLINK directly tackles one of the key barriers identified in Lightness, which limited the promotion of CECs in Poland and Germany: the lack of LRAs involvement and support. While covering this, and other key barriers related to engagement and technological uptake, PUBLINK scales up the Lightness Market Actors Community and Engagement Toolkit, by fostering public innovation (complementary to the socio-technological innovation of Lightness). TRA is a part of the LIGHTNESS project team.</p>
<p>LIFE-Step-WISE mission is to increase capacity of Local and Regional Authorities to initiate an effective energy transition through development of Clean Energy Transition Plans using Step-WISE toolkit to build dynamic CET policies to monitor progress towards targets.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will upscale the results and learnings from Step-WISE by utilising the Step-WISE toolkit to empower LRAs in the promotion of CET policies, and amplifying the governance support for a cross-sectoral assistance (adding disciplines and sectors to the digital training proposed by Step-WISE), and a more strategic and hands-on focus on the scalability that ECs can have (within the policy and holistic framework). CERES is a part of the Step-WISE project team.</p>

<p>LIFE-POWERYOUTH aims to empower young people between 15-30 years old to play an active role towards the energy transition by inter alia focusing on increasing youth participation in energy communities and triggering collective energy actions</p>	<p>The flow of know-how between PUBLINK and POWERYOUTH will take place thanks to the support of PNEC (LoS) through its information channels to the 40 members of the association and directly to the city of Siemiatycze in the form of participation in two workshops in the city and providing model of motivation young people to create energy communities</p>
<p>LIFE_REDI4HEAT, aims to support the implementation of key EU legislations on heating and cooling.</p>	<p>With their support, PUBLINK will learn from REDI4HEAT results and use their tools for renewable heating and cooling solutions. Their coordinator supports PUBLINK with a LoS.</p>
<p>CREST – Climate resilient coastal urban infrastructures through digital twinning 2022-2024 (URBAN EUROPE – ENUTS), aims to help urban areas implement platforms using augmented reality and digital twin technologies for climate resilience, decision-making, and policy innovation. Pilots in Kołobrzeg, Bordeaux, and Møre og Romsdal will support strong responses to climate change.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will use the collaborative framework from CREST to connect energy communities across cities, enabling knowledge-sharing and collective decision-making. This approach will help scale energy community models and foster cooperation between public authorities and stakeholders in different regions. IRMiR is a part of the CREST project team.</p>
<p>PopUpUrbanSpaces – Facilitating Shift Towards Active Forms of Mobility 2023-2026 (Interreg Central Europe) aims to shift residents' attitudes and behaviours toward sustainable urban mobility using tactical urbanism and placemaking. The project uses pop-up interventions to show how reducing car dominance in public spaces improves the urban environment in pilot cities across Central Europe.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will adopt the "show and tell" approach from PopUpUrbanSpaces to engage communities in energy transition activities. By using temporary urban interventions to demonstrate the benefits of energy communities, PUBLINK will help influence public behaviour and build stronger connections between residents and local authorities. IRMiR is a part of the PopUpUrbanSpaces project team.</p>

<p>ISEED – Inclusive Science and European Democracies 2021-2024 (Horizon 2020) aims to enhance the quality and legitimacy of political decision-making through knowledge-based deliberation and participative practices. The project explores how citizen participation in science can help overcome obstacles in democratic governance across Europe.</p>	<p>PUBLINK will build on ISEED’s methods of participative governance by integrating citizen-driven decision-making into energy community planning. Through knowledge-based deliberation, PUBLINK will empower local authorities and communities to co-create sustainable energy strategies, fostering deeper public involvement and democratic processes in energy transitions. IRMiR is a part of the ISEED project team.</p>
<p>LOCAL GoGREEN, aims to accelerate clean energy transition in rural areas by supporting local authorities and providing them assistance in their development of SECAPS and action plans on CET actions.</p>	<p>In the LOCAL GoGREEN projects pilot Albstadt, the major concern about clean energy application is that heat supply networks (the only possible - and sustainable - solution in historical areas of the town) cannot be implemented due to issues like unclear responsibilities. Therefore, the results, especially from the German pilot will be used to find solutions to provide sustainable heat (and cold). JER is part of the LOCAL GoGREEN team.</p>

Table 02_PUBLINK Upscaling results of other EU funded projects, from the Grant Agreement.

Given the large number of European projects related to energy communities, an ongoing assessment is being carried out to determine their priority for PUBLINK. This evaluation considers the thematic relevance of each project to PUBLINK’s objectives, as well as the level of connection or synergy with consortium partners. The prioritisation process will be progressively refined throughout the project duration and is expected to be consolidated by the time of the next update of this deliverable. In any case, the involvement of PUBLINK partners in these projects will make it easier for you to connect and collaborate.

b. LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM Sister Projects

Following the project’s start, additional projects have been identified thanks to CINEA’s invitation to a Microsoft Teams group, which includes initiatives funded under the LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM call and other similar ones. Most of these projects have already been contacted, and initial outreach has been carried out to explore potential synergies. However, the majority are set to begin operations in September 2025, while this deliverable is being prepared in August. By the next

update in April 2026, joint meetings are expected to have taken place, and collaboration formats will have been defined to enable coordinated work and knowledge exchange. Below we describe some of them and why we believe we can achieve interesting synergies.

LIFE_SHINE, Enabling Energy Communities to SHINE across Europe, 2025-2028

SHINE will equip Local and Regional Authorities (LRAs) with the skills and tools they need to maximise opportunities and support for community energy. They will have tools for LRAs in the Reescoop platform. Their energy communities will be focused on district heating, cooling, retrofitting, and renewable energy generation.

LIFE EnerGISE, Energy communities Effective Guidance, Advise, Innovative Support and Stimulation, 2025-2028

LIFE EnerGISE Project aims to streamline and promote the process of establishing and developing energy communities in Central Europe. They intend to test and establish pilot one-stop-shop centres for energy communities and cooperatives.

NESOIplus, New Energy Solutions Optimized for Island Outermost Regions, 2025-2028

NESOIplus goal is to facilitate bottom-up energy communities projects implementation (Islands). They will work on investment concepts, integrating support in business modelling and technical aspects, so that the project will be aligned with the investors' requirements and expectations, reference materials, tools, capacity building and matchmaking opportunities along the whole value chain of energy communities.

SHAREs Plus, Advancing Simple and Smart Energy Communities in Eastern Europe, 2025-2028

SHAREs Plus goal is to advance citizen-led energy initiatives in five European countries by leveraging frontrunner expertise, proven tools, and functional technical platforms.

We have already spoken with the coordinators of these projects, which began in September, and some have even invited us to their KoM. We will have a meeting with them once they are up and running. We will most likely lead a joint meeting with these sister projects. In the next update of this deliverable, it will be possible to detail the synergies between the projects.

c. Other ENERCOM Projects

These projects were also identified during our research, and we contacted most of them to explore synergies. Discussions have been held with the following:

LIFE21 CET LOOP, Local Ownership Of Power, 2022-2025¹

The main goal from LIFE_LOOP is to support cities and citizens in creating their energy community.²

This project has developed a comprehensive accreditation scheme for municipalities to support and engage with energy communities.

LIFE_LOOPS collects a [Self-Assessment Test from local authorities](#), which identifies the different ways and roles in which LRAS can support energy communities.

It includes capacity-building modules (e.g., [Community Energy Espresso course](#)), and a [matchmaking tool](#) connecting local authorities with energy communities through the listing of public assets (rooftops, land, etc.). Although municipal engagement is still limited due to time constraints, the project is building a network of accredited cities that could serve as a foundation for PUBLINK's coalition of public authorities. This tool could help PUBLINK to start the Coalition of cities and public authorities for energy communities.

They have also developed a [Policy Report](#) on the barriers encountered by LRAS, which could also serve as a basis for PUBLINK.

They plan to continue their work when in September 2025 their project ends with the [SPARKLE project](#) from Rescoop.

LIFE21-CET CONNECTHEAT, Community Engagement For Clean Heat, 2022-2025³

The main goal of ConnectHeat is to enable a policy framework for the development of community energy initiatives, aiming at decarbonising the heating and cooling (H&C) sector.

¹ Completed with information with an interview with Electra Energy, partner of LIFE-LOOP.

² mentioned in the RESCOOP interview we conducted with them about the context of energy communities.

³ completed with interview with the coordinating entity, AMBIENTE ITALIA SRL

They are disseminating the results the 8th and 9th of September at the The 19th International Symposium on District Heating and Cooling organised by [VITO](#) and [EnergyVille](#) under the umbrella of [IEA DHC](#).

The most relevant outputs of the ConnectHeat project for PUBLINK may be:

- the [map of examples](#) of thermal energy communities.
- the [training toolbox](#), with training (webinars) for local councils and training for trainers.
- Interesting publications such as the "[Regional Policy Roadmaps](#)" which offers an insight into key barriers and challenges encountered in the ConnectHeat's six focal areas (Belgium, Bulgaria Croatia, Germany, Italy, Spain) or "[Warmer \(and cooler\) together: Position Paper on Renewable Heating & Cooling for Energy Communities](#)" or the [Implementation of the pilot Cases](#), all related in different ways to heat-based energy communities, where we can also find the example of Gran Canaria.

ConnectHeat is connected with other projects —Plan4Cold, MUSE DHC, and SHINE—, enabling PUBLINK to stay connected with them and their networks.

[LIFE21-CET_BECKON, Boosting Energy Communities massive deployment by equipping local authorities with comprehensive technical assistance cookboOk, integrated services and capacity building, 2022-2025.](#)⁴

LIFE_BECKON Stimulates and boosts the deployment of Energy Communities across Europe by developing and delivering comprehensive support mechanisms for public authorities, promoters and Local Action Groups to better equip them to facilitate the creation of Energy Communities

The project ends in 2025, but they probably will get an extension to end in April 2026. They are supporting Local Authorities in 3 pilots (Ávila, Copenhagen, and Sofía) with service (OSS digital platform and technical assistance offices) and [capacity building](#). They are also offering the training to replicators through an open call.

Their technical assistance offices experience will help PUBLINK for the development of our Energy community pilots, the capacity building materials for Local authorities will be useful for ours and the cities that participated in the training for our Coalition of Cities for Energy Communities.

⁴ Information from the interview with R2M Spain, Partner from LIFE-BECKON.

LIFE21-CET_COMANAGE, Developing a transnational governance and holistic integrated services framework supporting the sustainability of European energy communities, 2022-2025⁵

COMANAGE aims to facilitate sustainability and growth in renewable energy communities by co-creating an open-source toolkit to support their governance and management.

The project ends in October 2025 but connections have already been set and synergies have been found.

The [training](#) and [tools](#) (technical, financial, dissemination, social, legal) developed for their project have been designed with the needs and contexts in Spain, Poland and Italy in mind. Therefore, the resources can be very useful for PUBLINK as a starting point for developing training or support schemes. The same applies to the [Decision Support System](#).

Therefore, the Comanage Open Platform contains documents that can be used in each stage of creating the energy community and can serve as a basis for our pilot projects.

LIFE21-CET_TANDEMS, Territorial Analysis of Decentralised Energy Markets, 2022-2025

TANDEMS aims to encourage collaboration between municipalities and energy cooperatives for a just and accelerated energy transition.

LIFE22-CET_COMET, Coalitions for Community Energy Catalyzation in Eastern EU, 2023-2026

LIFE-COMET aims to transform the community energy landscape in Central and Eastern Europe through assessment, experience sharing, and coalition building. It could be a beginning for The Coalition of Cities for Energy Communities in PUBLINK.

LIFE22-CET_ENCOM_HUM, Energy Community HUB - Developing supporting services for the creation of Energy Communities, 2024-2026

ENCOM-HUB aims to support the development of Energy Communities (ECs) owned and run by citizens, SMEs, and public authorities France (FR), Spain (ES), Italy (IT) and Bulgaria (BG).

⁵ completed with an interview with the coordinating entity, ECOSERVEIS.

LIFE22-CET_EC4RURAL, Fostering local engagement for Clean Energy Transition in Rural Areas through Energy Communities, 2023-2026

EC4RURAL aims to change the paradigm of local relations to boost Energy Communities in rural municipalities. Methodology for carrying out local energy analysis, Policy recommendations, capacity building material from their work will be useful for PUBLINK.

LIFE22-CET_ECOEMPOWER, ECOsystems EMPOWERing at regional and local scale supporting energy communities, 2023-2026

ECOEMPOWER aims to support regional authorities in their role of energy community facilitators through the creation of a One Stop Shop (OSS). Interesting LRAS' role in the energy communities.

d. Other similar LIFE-CET projects

LIFE23-CET_European Energy Communities Facility, 2024-2028

ENERCOM Facility will devote at least 7 million euros to provide direct support to emerging energy communities across Europe mostly in the form of lump sum grants. This facility offers capacity-building, financial support and resources to Energy Communities.

LIFE- ACCE, Access to Capital for Community Energy, 2022-2025

ACCE aims to develop and scale up collective financing tools for energy communities across Europe.

LIFE24-CET-MUSE DHC, coMmUnity-led actionS for Efficient DHC, 2025-2028

MUSE DGC fosters the diffusion of new efficient DHC networks, exploiting RES and waste heat in local chains and maximizing socio-economic and environmental benefits for communities.

LIFE23-CET-Plan4Cold, Supporting South Europe municipalities in the definition of Sustainable Local Heating and Cooling Plans, 2024-2027

Plan4Cold aims to support South European municipalities dealing with the obligation for municipalities with more than 45.000 inhabitants to prepare local heating and cooling plans.

LIFE22-CET-SET_HEAT, Supporting Energy Transition and Decarbonisation in District Heating Sector, 2023-2026

SET_HEAT aims to accelerate the energy transition and decarbonization of district heating in four targeted Eastern European countries through the integration of low-grade renewable and waste heat sources in high-temperature DH networks.

LIFE24-CET-POWER2PPL, Powering Community Energy Investments in Catalonia, 2025-2028

POWER2PPL aims to support public, private, citizen and social promoters of sustainable energy investments in the preparation and implementation of their projects including citizen-led renewable energy communities.

LIFE21-CET_OSR-Coop, One Stop Renovation Co-op, 2022-2025

OSR-Coop aims to advance cooperative One-Stop Shop (OSS) building renovation services throughout Europe, policy recommendations.

e. Other calls (Horizon, Interreg)⁶

Interreg REC4EU, Renewable Energy Communities for EU regions, 2023-2027⁷

REC4EU aims to reinforce or create regional support systems for the creation or development of RECs. Their Policy instruments could be used by PUBLINK.

Interreg PlanHeat, Local Heat Planning - Achieving the Heat Transition in BSR Municipalities, 2025-2028

PlanHeat's objective is the joint development of a transnational handbook that supports municipalities in the Baltic Sea region in the creation of local heat plans. To this end, solutions in the areas of data use, technology, training of municipal staff, stakeholder participation and financing will be developed, tested and summarised in the handbook. PUBLINK Partners NAPE and ACO are part of this project.

Interreg Green4Heat, Accelerating the uptake of green heating and cooling solutions across EU territories, 2024-2028

Green4Heat supports participating regions in advancing sustainable district heating by enhancing territorial heat planning, aligning policies to promote the uptake of

⁶ Only detailing the projects with priority 1 and 2 from the list developed.

⁷ Mentioned by Agencia Andaluza de la Energía when interviewing about ECs on their Region.

green technologies—such as heat pumps—and facilitating the deployment of state-of-the-art heat networks, all while actively engaging territorial stakeholders and citizens. As a partner in this initiative, EREN (a PUBLINK partner) plays a key role in bridging the outcomes of Green4Heat with our project. The main contribution to PUBLINK lies in the advancement of policy instruments, particularly the energy policy of Castilla y León, which is focused on updating the Regional Thermal Energy Strategy, thus providing valuable inputs for integrated and replicable policy frameworks within PUBLINK’s scope.

Interreg [Share RES](#), SHARing REnewable eneRgy through Energy communities, 2023-2027⁸

Share RES aims to improve the policies that enable active citizen participation in the energy market.

Interreg [DECA](#), The Danube Energy Communities Accelerator, 2024-2026

DECA aims to test how citizen-led renewable energy actions can be accelerated across the Danube Region. The consortium will develop a Danube Community Energy Acceleration Strategy for a network of community energy acceleration hubs that will sustain and expand support for community renewable energy action across the Danube Region, into the future. Development of financing mechanisms, multidisciplinary innovations and engagement of LRAs could be some connection with PUBLINK.

Interreg [NRGCOM](#), Creating appropriate operational conditions for renewable energy communities in the Danube Region, 2024-2026

NRGCOM builds on a multilevel approach. Within the project, the partners will review the legal frameworks, analyse the operation systems and governance techniques of existing RECs and collect best practices in the subject, in order to develop policy recommendations to remove bottlenecks. It will bring a broad approach to modelling EC potentially useful to PUBLINK.

Interreg [ESPON-TANDEM](#), Territorial Analysis of Decentralised Energy Markets, 2023-2026⁹

ESPON-TANDEM draws a policy trajectory for the efficient and inclusive uptake of energy communities. Recently published a mapping of energy communities across Europe, highlighting geographical disparities and correlations with national enabling

⁸ Mentioned by Emececuadrado when interviewing about ECs on their region

⁹ Mentioned by RESCOOP when interviewing them about Energy Communities in Europe

frameworks. This data will support PUBLINK’s spatial and contextual analysis of community energy development.

Horizon RESCHOOL, Strategies and tOOls for Incentivization and management of flexibility in Energy Communities with distributed Resources, 2023-2026

RESCHOOL aims to leverage energy communities as a formal way to aggregate active consumers and prosumers and empower them as relevant energy stakeholders.

Horizon Pro-Light, Progressive lighthouse districts serving as green district Gate towards Leadership in Sustainability, 2022-2026

Pro-Light aims to demonstrate 6 refurbished demo sites and energy communities in 6 European countries, allowing a smart neighbourhood approach and providing blueprints for replication.

H2020 CEES, Community energy for Energy Solidarity, 2021-2024¹⁰

CEES aims to deliver a toolkit of proven approaches by which community projects lift people out of energy poverty. It produced a practical "[Solidarity Toolkit](#)" on addressing energy poverty, featuring real-life examples and guidance on how energy communities—particularly from Local and Regional Authorities (LRAs)—can integrate vulnerable households through subsidized participation, social tariffs, and solidarity funds.

H2020 oPEN Lab, Open innovation living labs for Positive Energy Neighbourhoods, 2021-2026

oPEN Lab aims to identify replicable, commercially viable solution packages enabling the achievement of positive energy neighbourhoods within existing urban contexts that are seamlessly integrated into the local energy system as an active micro-energy hub, and to test these technologies and packages as an integrated solution at neighbourhood scale.

H2020 Sun4All, Eurosolar for all: energy communities for a fair energy transition in Europe, 2021-2024

Sun4All aims to help vulnerable households to switch to renewable energy while reducing their energy bills. Capacity Building on energy poverty and guidelines to

¹⁰ Mentioned by RESCOOP in their interview about Energy Communities in Europe.

integrate Energy poverty in SECAPS as well as the toolkit to help local Governments could be useful for PUBLINK.

Below is a summary table of all of them.

PUBLINK Sister and related Projects			
Acronym	Title	Duration	Priority ¹¹
H2020-RENAISSANCE	RENewAble Integration and SuStainAbility iN energy CommunitiEs	2019-2022	1
H2020-Lightness	market uptake of citizen energy communities enabLing a HIGH peneTratioN of renewable Energy SourceS	2020-2023	2
H2020-Sun4All	Eurosolar for all: energy communities for a fair energy transition in Europe	2021-2024	2
H2020- CEES	Community energy for Energy Solidarity	2021-2024	2
H2020- SCCALE 203050	Sustainable Collective Citizen Action for a Local Europe 20-30-50	2021-2024	2
H2020- oPEN Lab	Open innovation living labs for Positive Energy Neighbourhoods	2021-2026	2
LIFE-ACCE	Access to Capital for Community Energy	2022-2025	1
LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM LIFE-LOOP	Local Ownership Of Power	2022-2025	1
LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM CONNECTHEAT	COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT FOR CLEAN HEAT	2022-2025	1
LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM COMANAGE	Developing a transnational governance and holistic integrated services framework supporting the sustainability of European energy communities	2022-2025	2
LIFE OSR-Coop	OSR - One Stop Renovation Co-op	2022-2025	1
LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM BECKON	Boosting Energy Communities massive deployment by equipping local authorities with comprehensive technical assistance cookBoOk, integrated services and capacity buildiNg	2022-2025	1
LIFE CET-2021-ENERCOM TANDEMS	Territorial Analysis of Decentralised Energy Markets	2022-2025	1
LIFE-2021-CET-POLICY REDI4HEAT	RED implementation for heating and cooling	2022-2025	2
HORIZON-CL4- Pro-Light	Progressive lighthouse districts serving as green district Gate towards Leadership in Sustainability	2022-2026	2
LIFE-2022-CET SET_HEAT	Supporting Energy Transition and Decarbonisation in District Heating Sector	2023-2026	2
HORIZON-RESCHOOL	Strategies and tOOls for Incentivization and management of flexibility in Energy Communities with distributed Resources	2023-2026	1

¹¹ Priority established according to connection and relevance to our project

LIFE CET-2022-ENERCOM COMET	Coalitions for Community Energy Catalyzation in Eastern EU	2023-2026	1
LIFE CET-2022-ENERCOM EC4RURAL	Fostering local engagement for Clean Energy Transition in Rural Areas through Energy Communities	2023-2026	1
LIFE CET-2022-ENERCOM ECOEMPOWER	ECOsystems EMPOWERing at regional and local scale supporting energy communities	2023-2026	2
Interreg- ESPON-TANDEM	Territorial Analysis of Decentralised Energy Markets	2023-2026	2
Interreg- REC4EU	Renewable Energy Communities for EU regions	2023-2027	1
Interreg- Share RES	SHARing REnewable eneRgy through Energy communitieS	2023-2027	2
HORIZON-REFORMERS	Regional Ecosystems FOR Multiple-Energy Resilient Systems	2023-2028	1
Interreg-DECA	The Danube Energy Communities Accelerator	2024-2026	2
Interreg-NRGCOM	Creating appropriate operational conditions for renewable energy communities in the Danube Region	2024-2026	2
LIFE CET-2022-ENERCOM ENCOM HUB	Energy Community HUB - Developing supporting services for the creation of Energy Communities	2024-2026	2
LIFE22-CET POWERYOUTH	Empowering youth for energy community actions	2024-2026	2
LIFE23-CET-Plan4Cold	Supporting South Europe municipalities in the definition of Sustainable Local Heating and Cooling Plans	2024-2027	2
LIFE CET-2023 ENERCOM Facility	European Energy Communities Facility	2024-2028	1
Interreg-Green4Heat	Accelerating the uptake of green heating and cooling solutions across EU territories	2024-2028	2
LIFE24-CET-PDA POWER2PPL	Powering Community Energy Investments in Catalonia	2025-2028	2
LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM SHINE	Enabling Energy Communities to SHINE across Europe	2025-2028	1
LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM SHAREs Plus	Advancing Simple and Smart Energy Communities in Eastern Europe	2025-2028	1
LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM NESOIplus	New Energy Solutions Optimized for Island Outermost Regions	2025-2028	2
Interreg-PlanHeat	Local Heat Planning - Achieving the Heat Transition in BSR Municipalities	2025-2028	2
LIFE CET-2024-ENERCOM LIFE EnerGISE	Energy communities Effective Guidance, Advise, Innovative Support and Stimulation	2025-2028	1
LIFE24-CET-DH MUSE DHC	coMmUnity-led actionS for Efficient DHC	2025-2028	1

Table 03_List of PUBLINK sister and related projects.

f. Projects Mapping

The following image provides a visual representation of the sister and related project mapping, illustrating the landscape of initiatives related to LIFE-PUBLINK. At the core of the map are projects funded under the respective LIFE call, LIFE-CET-2024-ENERCOM, highlighted to emphasize their close alignment in objectives and timing. Surrounding these are other relevant projects from previous LIFE-ENERCOM calls, additional LIFE programme projects, and initiatives funded under different EU programmes (Horizon, Interreg), each distinguished by a specific colour as indicated in the legend.

The spatial distribution of projects across the map is organized thematically, with clusters reflecting key areas such as Financing, Rural and Island contexts, OSS (One Stop Shop) and services, Building Renovation, Heating and Cooling, Capacity Building as well as Policies and Governance. The latter category is further subdivided into Renewable Energy Policies, Energy Poverty, Citizen Participation, and Local and Regional Authorities (LRAs), allowing for a more nuanced understanding of policy-related synergies.

A central feature of the map is the identification of projects linked to energy communities, most of which fall within a dedicated circular boundary, underscoring their shared focus. Projects located outside this circle are those with more tangential or indirect connections to this specific theme.

Overall, the map aims not only to highlight thematic proximity and potential synergies—such as the replication, upscaling or integration of results, joint activities, or mutual learning—but also to clarify which projects offer opportunities for sustained collaboration and knowledge transfer, and which are rather disconnected in terms of objectives, scope or outcomes.

- LIFE CET_2024_ENERCOM
- LIFE CET_2023_ENERCOM FACILITY
- LIFE CET_2022_2021_ENERCOM
- OTHER LIFE
- OTHER CALLS

Image 01_Sister Projects Map: EU projects classified according to their thematic proximity to PUBLINK

Future updates to this deliverable will likely include additional projects that have not yet been identified, and some others no longer considered relevant may disappear.

As indicated in the previous section, most of them will be useful to us in applying and/or building-up on their results.

3. Lighthouse Energy Communities

As outlined in the previous sections, the scope of this deliverable is expanding beyond the mapping of EU-funded sister projects to include a deeper understanding of the energy community landscape. To this end, a contextual analysis has been conducted in key regions within the PUBLINK consortium—specifically in Spain (at national and regional levels), Poland, and Germany—through interviews with national and regional umbrella organisations representing energy communities. These entities provided valuable insights into the emergence, development, and operational realities of energy communities in their respective contexts. The following section presents a comparative overview of these national and regional landscapes, highlighting common trends, key differences, and the diverse enabling environments that shape the development of lighthouse energy communities across Europe.

a. Distribution and Context in Europe

Thanks to the interview in August 2025 with RESCOOP, relevant information was obtained about the distribution and status of energy communities in Europe.

Energy communities in Europe have deep historical roots, predating the formal EU definition established by the Clean Energy Package in 2019. Early examples include community-owned energy grids in Germany in the 19th century and the first community wind turbines in Denmark in the 1970s. However, their recent growth has been closely tied to the establishment of enabling legal frameworks. Countries that have transposed the EU directives effectively—such as Belgium, the Netherlands, Italy, Greece, and Czechia—show significant development, while nations without supportive legislation (e.g., Sweden, Malta, Slovakia, Romania) have minimal or no registered communities.

Geographically, there is a clear north-south divide in technological focus: Southern and Eastern European countries (e.g., Spain, Italy, Greece) are dominated by solar PV and self-consumption projects, driven by high solar potential and lower capital requirements. In contrast, Northwest Europe (Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Denmark) sees more wind, heating and cooling systems, and building renovation initiatives, often involving higher investment and more complex governance.

The cooperative model is the most common legal structure, aligning with the democratic, non-profit principles enshrined in EU legislation. While Member States have flexibility in legal forms, cooperatives remain dominant due to their suitability for participatory governance. Most communities are citizen-led, often initiated by NGOs or local activists, with increasing involvement from municipalities in recent

years—though formal partnerships between citizens and public authorities still represent a minority (estimated at around 10%). Larger, mature communities are beginning to federate nationally (e.g., Union Renovables in Spain, SEACOOOP in Belgium), creating secondary cooperatives capable of participating in large-scale projects such as offshore wind tenders.

Despite strong citizen motivation—driven by energy affordability, local resilience, climate action, and social cohesion—many communities face significant barriers to implementation. Key challenges include limited access to financing, especially for capital-intensive technologies; grid connection delays; lack of dedicated legal and administrative support; and risks of corporate capture, where private actors mimic community models to access public incentives. Additionally, while digital tools for energy management and member engagement are emerging (like smart metering and management platforms), their adoption is still limited and rarely supported by public authorities.

Regarding financial mechanisms, energy communities rely primarily on member self-financing, with typical investments of around €2,500 per member for solar projects. This is increasingly complemented by EU funding (Horizon, LIFE, ERDF, Social Climate Fund) and by support from ethical banks and financial cooperatives, particularly in Northwest Europe. Innovative instruments such as crowdfunding, revolving funds managed by national federations, and the emerging REScoop Energy Fund (formerly referred to as MiSEIS)—a pan-European lending facility by major energy cooperatives—are helping to scale up community-led investments. However, access to these mechanisms remains uneven across regions, highlighting the need for more harmonized and accessible financial support structures.

Selected Real Examples of Energy Communities in Europe (outside Germany, Poland and Spain)

Federation Europeenne De Finances Et Banques Ethiques Et Alternatives (FEBEA) gathered these real Energy Communities from different countries in Europe:

Energy Communities in Europe				
Name	Location	Country	Legal Form	Most interesting ¹²
Irish Sustainable	Dunleer and Louth region	Ireland	Company limited by guarantee (social enterprise)	Air-source heat pumps,

¹² Many more fields were compiled. For now, we will only detail what we found most interesting about that Energy Community.

Communities Together (ISCT)				and other activity, LRA's role, Financing actors
Galway Energy Co-op	Galway	Ireland	Cooperative	Interesting for financing mechanisms, Energy poverty examples
Fondo Saccà // Maregrosso Community Hub	Messina	Italy	Social Energy Community (This is probably not the legal denomination but just the setting under which they operate- probably they do not have a legal form perse)	Energy poverty, activities, LRA role, Participation
ÉNERGIES PARTAGÉES EN ALSACE	KINGERSHEIM, Alsace	France	Cooperative	Financing mechanisms, participation,
ENERGIES CITOYENNES	Colayrac-Saint-Cirq, Lot-et-Garonne dep	France	Cooperative	Participation, Financing
CITOY'ENR	Toulouse	France	"Coopérative SCIC (Société Coopérative d'Intérêt Collectif)"	Participation, Financing
COOPEOS	Fernelmont, Namur	Belgium	Cooperative (Société Coopérative)	Biomass, LRAs role
COURANT D'AIR	Elsenborn	Belgium	Cooperative Limited Liability (SCRL FS); social-purpose enterprise	Activities, objectives, LRAs role
Energy Community Of Karditsa (ESEK)	Thessaly	Greece	Energy Community	Biomass, E poverty, participation

b. Distribution and Context in Germany

Historical background

The development began in the mid-2000s with the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG), whose feed-in tariff and 20-year guarantee triggered a founding wave of energy communities. With declining subsidies, risks increased; many communities professionalised and developed new business models such as tenant electricity and PPAs.

Numbers and current status

Within the German Cooperative and Raiffeisen Confederation (DGRV), about 950-1,000 energy cooperatives are organised. In total, about 1,050 energy communities had been founded since 2006, with around 220,000 members, €3.6 billion in investments and about 8 TWh annual electricity production (as of 31 Dec 2024). The average community has about 380 members.

Distribution

Energy communities are unevenly distributed: there is more diversity in rural regions, while urban areas such as the Ruhr district show fewer initiatives. In addition, a West–East divide persists; in eastern Germany, small communities are less common.

Legal form and governance

Energy communities are almost exclusively registered cooperatives (eG). Governance follows the principle “one member, one vote,” with general assemblies, supervisory boards, and auditing by regional associations.

Actors

The movement is strongly citizen-driven, often supported by municipalities that initiate founding processes and provide land. A key role is played by the umbrella communities Bürgerwerke, which bundles electricity trading and services for its members.

Technologies

Energy communities are active across all fields (PV, wind, heat, mobility). Solar PV dominates, but district heating is the fastest-growing sector. Wind is capital-intensive and legally uncertain; storage is gaining importance, mainly for financial reasons. Future topics include power-to-heat, car-sharing models, and regional balancing groups.¹³

¹³ Source: DGRV interview, August 2025; DGRV Survey 2024 – Energy Cooperatives in Numbers

Financing

The main pillars are member shares, bank loans, and subordinated loans. Crowdfunding is discussed but plays practically no role.

Barriers

Energy communities face several hurdles: high investment costs for wind projects, the complexity of grid connection, and declining EEG support, which increases risks for communities often run on a voluntary basis. In addition, there is still a lack of legal clarity regarding the planned energy sharing.

Selected Real Examples of Energy Communities in Germany

PUBLINK German partners (Dr. Jakob energy research GmbH & Co. KG (JER) and Aconium (ACO) gathered the following Energy Communities:

Energy Communities in Germany			
Name	Location	Legal Form	Most interesting ¹⁴
ErdwärmeDich Anergienetze eG	Bremen	Cooperative	Geothermal Energy, Energy poverty, participation
Nahwärme Eichkamp (Local Heating Eichkamp)	Berlin	Cooperative	Geothermal Energy, participation
kliQ-Berlin	Berlin	Cooperative	Geothermal heating and building renovation, Schools, participation, some LRA participation
Bürgerenergie Nord	Norderstedt (near Hamburg)	Cooperative	Financial mechanisms, LRAs role
EWS Elektrizitätswerke Schönau eG	Schönau im Schwarzwald	Cooperative	Energy poverty actions, wind energy

¹⁴ Many more fields were compiled. For now, we will only detail what we found most interesting about that Energy Community.

Energiegenossenschaft Starkenburg eG	Heppenheim / Landkreis Bergstraße	Cooperative	Solar PV, wind, biogas; Citizen wind turbine, participation; E-mobility
Heidelberger Energiegenossenschaft eG	Heidelberg	Cooperative	Solar PV, tenant electricity; Wind energy, e+KUBATOR

c. Distribution and Context in Poland

Thanks to Narodowa Agencja Poszanowania Energii S.A.(NAPE)'s answers in August 2025, relevant information was obtained about the distribution and status of energy communities in Poland.

Historical background

Energy communities in Poland began to emerge following the transposition of RED II into national law through amendments to the Renewable Energy Sources (RES) Act in 2018. However, significant growth has occurred since 2023–2025, driven by supportive regulatory frameworks, public funding opportunities, and increasing awareness. As of July 2025, 207 energy cooperatives are registered in the National Court Register (KRS), with 106 also listed in the KOWR agricultural support register, reflecting active development.

Distribution

Their distribution is highly uneven, concentrated in rural and urban-rural municipalities, as current legislation restricts energy cooperatives to these areas. Notable activity is observed in regions such as Lublin Voivodeship (e.g., Hrubieszów) and areas supported by regional initiatives like RENALDO in Kuyavian-Pomeranian and Podlaskie Voivodeships, which provide technical assistance and incubation for new cooperatives. The requirement to operate within a single DSO’s network further limits geographic scalability.

Legal form and governance

The dominant legal form is the energy cooperative, established under the RES Act and governed by the Cooperative Law or the Act on Farmers’ Cooperatives. This model is preferred due to its clear regulatory recognition, access to preferential settlement mechanisms (e.g., reduced distribution fees, group net-billing), and eligibility for dedicated support schemes. Although the legal framework also allows

for Citizen Energy Communities (OSE), this model remains less developed and offers fewer operational benefits, making cooperatives the de facto "working model" in practice.

Actors

Most communities are initiated by a combination of local governments, local entrepreneurs, and farmers, with municipalities often playing a leading role as founding members or coordinators—helping to aggregate demand, secure land, and negotiate with DSOs. While this reflects a top-down facilitation model, there is a growing trend toward broader citizen participation.

The main actors driving energy communities in Poland are local governments, local entrepreneurs, farmers, technical operators (RES developers), and support organisations such as CoopTech Hub. Since mid-2025, the National Auditing Union of Energy Cooperatives has also emerged as a key player in promoting standardisation, representation, and dialogue with regulatory bodies.

Technologies

Technologically, solar PV dominates, particularly in small-scale and distributed installations. However, a shift is underway toward hybrid models combining PV with wind and biogas, especially in areas with suitable resources. Storage is not yet widespread, but thermal storage is emerging in biogas and district heating projects. The most advanced cooperatives are developing mixed-technology portfolios to enhance energy stability and self-consumption.

Barriers

Despite this growing ecosystem, the development of energy communities faces significant barriers. Frequent changes in energy legislation—particularly regarding net-billing rules—create regulatory uncertainty and discourage long-term investment. Grid connection delays and unresponsive distribution system operators (DSOs) are the most critical bottlenecks, often causing project delays of several months or more. Additional legal constraints, such as the restriction to rural and urban-rural municipalities, the requirement to operate within a single DSO network, and the obligation to cover at least 70% of members' energy demand from self-generation, further limit scalability and prevent replication in urban areas. Low levels of digitisation among public and state-owned entities also hinder data access, monitoring, and automated energy settlements.

Financing

Energy communities in Poland are primarily financed through a combination of member contributions—often supplemented by municipal equity—public grants from the Ministry of Climate and Environment and EU funding programmes, as well as loans from institutions such as BGK (National Development Bank). Bridging financing is frequently used when grant disbursements are delayed. While models like crowdfunding or cooperative investment schemes align with the community-driven ethos, they are not yet widely implemented. Instead, traditional funding sources—grants and loans—remain dominant. Some local cooperative banks are beginning to support payment handling and financial management, but dedicated community finance mechanisms such as revolving funds or Community Energy Financing Schemes (CEFS) are not yet operational at scale. The establishment of the National Auditing Union may, however, lay the groundwork for future collective financing solutions.

Selected Real Examples of Energy Communities in Poland

Our Polish partner NAPE highlighted the following energy communities, although their activity is based solely on photovoltaics and some information from them is still missing:

Energy Communities in Poland		
Name	Legal Form	Description
MES-TOWN ŁÓDŹ	Non-profit association	First in Poland to be entered into the Register of Citizen Energy Communities maintained by URE in April 2025. Grassroots social movement whose goal is to provide people with affordable energy and to help institutions solve problems with the electricity grid, but still no public authorities are involved.
Spółdzielnia Energetyczna	Cooperative	Nasza Energia, the highest number of members (24)

Spółdzielnia Energetyczna Stawiski	Cooperative	One of the highest number of installations (121)
Spółdzielnia Energetyczna Gminy Wiejskiej Hrubieszów, Trzeszczany, Werbkowice	Cooperative	One of the most engaged: its representative was involved in the creation of the National Audit Union of Energy Cooperatives and became the CEO of the Union.

d. Distribution and Context in Spain

National Scale

Thanks to the interview in August 2025 with the ECODES Foundation, which manages the Observatorio Energía Común, Spain’s national observatory on energy communities, very relevant information was obtained about the distribution and status of energy communities in Spain.

Historical background

Energy communities in Spain began gaining traction after the 2019 Royal Decree (RD 244/2019), which enabled collective self-consumption. The first officially recognized community, Comptem by Enercoop in Crevillent, was launched in 2022. Since then, growth has accelerated, supported by national funding schemes like IMPLEMENTA (IDAE) and regional initiatives. By the end of 2024, there were 659 energy communities registered in Spain¹⁵.

Distribution

The development is highly uneven, concentrated in Navarre, Basque Country, Catalonia, and Valencia, which key drivers include: strong public support from regional and local governments, a tradition of cooperative and associative culture, the presence of electricity distribution cooperatives (e.g., 16 in Valencia).

¹⁵ According to the Observatorio Energía Común.

Legal form and governance

There is a 50/50 split between cooperatives and associations, with the latter gaining popularity due to simpler, lower-cost setup. Most communities are citizen-led (92%), with municipalities involved as members in only 21% of cases. If so, they act as facilitators (62%) and promoters (32%), providing meeting spaces, funding legal setup, or launching calls for support.

Technologies and activities

Over 95% focus on solar PV, due to its modularity, maturity, and cost-effectiveness. Other technologies (wind, biomass, heating/cooling) are rare. Battery storage is emerging but still exceptional. Some communities are exploring shared e-mobility and energy storage, though not yet widespread.

Notably, 52% of communities actively address energy poverty, through solidarity funds or subsidized access.

Barriers and financing

Key challenges include: lack of a clear national regulatory framework (Despite RD 5/2023 recognizing energy communities, detailed rules on governance, taxation, and rights are pending); complex and non-standardized grid connection processes; limited access to financing (63% rely on member contributions, 58% on public grants, traditional banks remain hesitant due to small scale and lack of collateral).

Regional Scale_ Basque Country

Energy communities in the Basque Country¹⁶ began to emerge around 2020, with a significant increase in new initiatives linked to the establishment of local support structures such as the Energy Community Transformation Offices (OTCs) and Energiaren Puntua, which provide technical assistance, training, and funding facilitation. Their distribution is highly uneven, concentrated primarily in the province of Gipuzkoa, where the presence of these dedicated OTCs has been a key driver of development. This geographical imbalance reflects the direct correlation between institutional support and community growth, as regions with active technical and administrative assistance have seen exponential growth compared to areas without such support mechanisms.

¹⁶ From answers made by Mondragon University in Basque Country (Spain)

These ECs are primarily citizen-led initiatives, often promoted through strong local collaboration between municipalities, citizens, and small businesses. The most common legal form is the cooperative, particularly within the network of Energiaren Puntua. Public authorities play an active role, with many communities involving local councils as partners, contributing land, rooftops, or financial support. Despite this enabling environment, key barriers remain, including administrative complexity, grid connection delays, and a lack of comprehensive regulatory clarity at the national level. Financing is predominantly based on member contributions, supported significantly by public grants at local and regional levels (e.g., from EVE – Basque Energy Agency). Most communities are residential in nature, with an average size of around 86 households, and focus on solar PV installations.

Regional Scale_ Catalonia

Energy communities in Catalonia¹⁷ began to emerge prominently in 2021, driven by a strategic initiative from the Osona County Council’s Energy Transition Office ([NEO](#)), which catalysed the creation of the first local communities. Their development has been closely tied to the presence of strong regional support networks, particularly Som Comunitats, which fosters collaboration among existing communities. The geographical distribution is uneven, with early activity concentrated in areas like Osona, reflecting a model where institutional backing at the comarcal (county) level plays a decisive role in enabling project development. Most communities are citizen-led and typically adopt the legal form of a cooperative, building on the region’s strong cooperative tradition. Public authorities act primarily as facilitators—providing meeting spaces, technical support, and funding calls—though direct municipal membership remains limited. Key barriers include administrative delays, grid connection bottlenecks, and complex access to public funding. Financing relies mainly on member contributions and public grants, with limited use of innovative financial mechanisms. While solar PV dominates, some communities like Arbúcies and La Tonenca have integrated biomass, and others are exploring shared e-mobility.

Regional Scale_ Extremadura

Energy communities in Extremadura¹⁸ began to emerge with the support of local Energy Community Transformation Offices (OTCs), which have played a crucial role in their formation, having helped to establish more than 10 communities. Their development is highly uneven, concentrated in areas with direct OTC involvement, reflecting a strong dependence on local institutional support. Most communities are not citizen-led but rather initiated by municipalities, which often need guidance due

¹⁷ From answers made by Som Comunitats in Catalunya (Spain)

¹⁸ From answers by Emececuadrado (OTC in Extremadura) (Spain).

to widespread energy sector illiteracy, especially in small, aging rural towns. The predominant legal form is the cooperative, though administrative and financial barriers within local governments limit their active participation as members. Key barriers include the lack of economic support, overly specific national funding schemes (e.g., CE-IMPLEMENTA) that are difficult to access, and lengthy development processes—often taking up to 1.5 years. Financing relies almost entirely on member contributions, as public funding has proven insufficient or inaccessible. While most projects focus on solar PV self-consumption, there is one known community using hydroelectric power, and another exploring shared mobility in Granada.

Selected Real Examples of Energy Communities in Spain

The Spanish partners have gathered these Energy Communities in Spain:

Energy Communities in Spain			
Name	Location	Legal Form	Most interesting ¹⁹
Asociacion de Usuarios Guadalix de la Sierra Genera	Guadalix de la Sierra	Association	Biomass, ESCO funding
Manza Energía	Manzanares El Real	Association	Energy poverty, participation, LRA role
Energía Bonita	La Palma, Islas Canarias	Cooperative	Energy poverty, LRA role, participation
Eco-Almócita	Almócita (Almería)	Cooperative	Energy poverty, rural development
La Tonenca	Tona (Barcelona)	Cooperative	Energy poverty, financing mechanisms
COSPES Cooperativa Santperenca d'Energia Sostenible	Sant Pere de Torelló (Barcelona)	Cooperative	building renovation
Playa del Inglés Gran Canaria	San Bartolomé de Tirajana	Association	Thermal EC

¹⁹ Many more fields were compiled. For now, we will only detail what we found most interesting about that Energy Community.

Spanish Regional comparison _ Andalusia, Catalonia, Basque Country, Extremadura²⁰

Energy communities in Spain are emerging unevenly across regions, shaped by local governance, administrative support, and pre-existing cooperative cultures. A common trend across Andalusia, Extremadura, Catalonia, and the Basque Country is that most initiatives are citizen-led, often starting from grassroots groups or local associations. However, their development is heavily influenced by the level of institutional support, which ranges from proactive facilitation to bureaucratic inertia.

The legal forms used are diverse but predominantly associations or cooperatives. Associations are preferred for their simplicity (Andalusia, Catalonia), while cooperatives are favoured in the Basque Country and Extremadura for their long-term governance structure. In Catalonia, the comarcal councils (e.g., Osona) have played a key role in funding and coordination, while in the Basque Country, OTCs (Offices for Energy Communities) and Energiaren Puntua act as central hubs for knowledge sharing and support.

A key commonality is the dominance of solar PV, with limited integration of storage or heating/cooling systems, and shared mobility on the rise. Financing relies primarily on member contributions, complemented by public grants (e.g., IMPLEMENTA, regional aids). However, access is often complex and slow, especially in Extremadura, where national funding was too restrictive to be useful.

Significant barriers are shared: bureaucratic delays, particularly in grid connection (e.g., Iberdrola's delays in Catalonia and the Basque Country), lack of technical capacity in public administrations, and low digitalisation. The absence of a clear national regulatory framework remains a structural challenge.

Despite these hurdles, public authorities play a crucial role. Andalusia has launched a 10-point roadmap, the Basque Country provides direct subsidies and technical support, and Catalonia benefits from strong regional coordination. In contrast, Extremadura reports limited institutional support, slowing progress.

²⁰ From interviews made to: Junta Andaluza de la Energía, Som Comunitats, OTC Emececuadrado and University of Mondragón.

In summary, while citizen motivation is strong, the success of energy communities depends on proactive, coordinated public support, and streamlined administrative processes. Regions with dedicated structures and funding show higher consolidation rates, highlighting the need for institutional capacity-building as a key success factor.

e. Comparative European overview

Comparative Overview of Energy Communities in Europe, Spain, Poland and Germany				
Aspect	European Level (EU-wide)	Poland	Spain	Germany
Moment of origin / key enabling framework	Post-2019 (Clean Energy Package transposition); growing momentum since 2020–2022	2018 (RES Act amendments); acceleration from 2023–2025	2019 (RD 244/2019 on collective self-consumption); first community in 2022	mid-2000s with the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG)
Distribution	Uneven: strong correlation with enabling national frameworks (e.g., Belgium, Netherlands, Italy, Greece) vs. limited presence in countries without legislation (e.g., Sweden, Romania)	Highly uneven; concentrated in rural and urban-rural municipalities (legal restriction); hotspots in Lublin, Kuyavian-Pomeranian, and Podlaskie Voivodeships	Uneven; concentrated in Navarre, Basque Country, Catalonia, and Valencia (linked to regional support and cooperative tradition)	Uneven distribution: more diverse in rural areas; fewer initiatives in urban areas (e.g., Ruhr) and eastern Germany.
Predominant legal form	Cooperative (most common and aligned with EU directives); some flexibility	Energy cooperative (under Cooperative or Farmers' Cooperatives	50% cooperatives, 50% associations; shift towards associations	Energy communities are almost exclusively registered

	for associations, LLCs, etc., depending on Member State	Law); de facto dominant model due to regulatory benefits	due to lower setup costs and simplicity	cooperatives (eG).
Main barriers	Grid access delays, lack of financing, regulatory uncertainty, risk of corporate capture, low municipal capacity	Frequent legislative changes, DSO bottlenecks, rural-only limitation, single-DSO rule, low digitisation in public entities	Lack of comprehensive national regulatory framework, complex grid connection processes, limited access to financing, administrative burden in public institutions	High investment costs (especially for wind), complex grid connections, phase-out of EEG support, and lack of legal clarity on energy sharing create financial and regulatory risks for volunteer-run communities.
Key promoters / leading actors	Citizen-led initiatives, NGOs; increasing municipal involvement via accreditation schemes (e.g., LIFE-LOOP)	Local governments, farmers, local entrepreneurs, technical operators; municipalities often act as initiators or coordinators	Citizen-led (92%); municipalities play key facilitator/promoter role (62% facilitation, 32% promotion), but low membership (21%)	Strongly citizen-driven, with municipal support in founding and land provision; umbrella organisations like Bürgerwerke play a key role in aggregation and service provision.
Dominant technologies	Solar PV (dominant, specially SW Europe), wind (NW Europe), heating/cooling	Solar PV (over 95%), with emerging hybrid models (PV + wind + biogas)	Solar PV (>95%); limited but growing interest in shared	Solar PV dominates; district heating is fastest-growing. Wind faces

	g, and building renovation (stronger increase in North Europe)		e-mobility and storage	legal and investment barriers.
Common financing mechanisms	Member contributions, EU funding (Horizon, LIFE), ethical banks, crowdfunding; emerging CEFS and revolving funds	Member contributions (often with municipal equity), public grants (national/EU), loans (e.g., BGK); limited use of innovative models	Member contributions, public grants; limited bank or innovative finance	Member contributions, bank loans, and subordinated loans.

4. Conclusions

First and foremost, it should be noted that this is a living document, and it will be updated in M11 to incorporate new insights, map progress through synergies and linkages with related European projects, provide a deeper understanding of the framework conditions of energy communities in these countries, or add relevant examples from each of the study regions.

a. European Related Projects

It is worth highlighting that, from Section 1 on European projects related to PUBLINK, the following observation has been made:

There exists a very extensive list of related projects, particularly concerning energy communities, but also covering other areas of interest—such as heating and cooling projects or financing mechanisms—which we will likely continue to explore in greater depth over the coming months as the project progresses.

Many of these related projects have generated valuable resources (e.g., publications, training materials, examples of energy communities, stakeholder networks, etc.) that could prove highly relevant and useful for various tasks within the PUBLINK project.

Most projects funded under the LIFE24-CET-ENERCOM call will commence in September 2025, and PUBLINK has already begun establishing contacts among consortiums. It is intended to raise synergies through knowledge sharing and collaborative work on specific tasks.

b. Lighthouse Energy Communities

This initial analysis of lighthouse energy communities, while not exhaustive, has provided valuable insights into the diverse framework conditions across European regions—shedding light on their origins, legal and organisational typologies, geographical distribution, and the technologies they employ or are beginning to adopt. It has also identified the key actors driving their development and the varying roles of public authorities. The findings reveal notable differences between regions, particularly in preferred legal forms and technological focus, while also highlighting common challenges—such as administrative barriers and limited access to financing—as well as shared reliance on citizen initiative and public support. As expected, countries with longer-standing initiatives and more developed regulatory frameworks show greater maturity and diversity in community energy models. Furthermore, the analysis underscores the importance of an associative and

cooperative culture, particularly evident in the regional experiences within Spain, for the emergence of bottom-up energy communities. Since this deliverable will be updated throughout the project, definitive conclusions are not yet possible. However, this preliminary mapping serves as a baseline for identifying good practices and relevant models that will inform subsequent project tasks, enabling deeper engagement and learning from these lighthouse cases in the coming phases.

Annex A: Consolidated Questionnaire

1. General and Energy Community framework

Question
<p>How is the distribution of energy communities across the region? Is it uniform? In which regions have they developed the most and/or have the greatest variety of projects? What do you think are the reasons for this?</p>
<p>Evolution of Energy Communities in the region</p> <p>Ppal_ How would you describe the evolution of energy communities in this region? When did they start to emerge and what's their current situation like?</p> <p>optional- What year did energy communities start to be created (in this region)? What would you say was the incentive that facilitated this? How has it evolved since then, and are there any visible trends? What stage/level of progress are most of them in? (creation, development, first project, consolidation or more than one project) How long does it usually take from idea to operation?</p> <p>How many energy communities do you have now in your association/federation?</p>
<p>What is the average size and typology of members of the Energy Communities you represent (residential, industrial, public institutions)?</p>
<p>What type of legal form is most common, and what would you say is the reason for this, and has it changed over time? (association, cooperative, others)</p>
<p>Public Authorities facilitation and role in ECs</p>

Question

>> How do usually public authorities (local, regional, or national governments) **support or regulate** the development of energy communities? Are there specific policies, incentives, or legal frameworks in place?

>> What percentage would you say that **local authorities empower, engage, facilitate** energy communities in their locality?

Which **stakeholders** usually take the lead in promoting energy communities in your region, and what role do they play in their development?

Citizen participation

How involved are citizens in the planning, decision-making, and operation of energy communities in your region?

- Level of participation
- models or mechanisms used to facilitate participation (e.g., assemblies, cooperative structures, digital platforms, voting systems)
- citizen-led initiative
- Comply with Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) definition of Energy Communities?

To what extent do they address the fight against **energy poverty**?

>> Could you give some examples?

2. Administrative and management tools

Question

In general, are energy communities carrying out **management internally or contracting it out** to other entities?

Digital tools and platforms

What role have digital tools or platforms played in energy communities in your region, and have public administrations supported their use?

- Which digital tools or platforms are most commonly used by energy communities for **administrative tasks like member communication** or decision-making?
- specific tools used for technical functions such as **monitoring** or managing energy systems
- platforms or approaches have worked best for **internal communication**
- **Exchange of information** (internal and external)
- Have **public authorities** promoted or facilitated the use of any of these technologies? If so, which ones and how?

3. Socio-technological challenges

Question

What are the **main challenges** energy communities encounter, and how have they generally overcome them?

>> What legal, technical, financial, or bureaucratic barriers currently hinder the introduction and use of innovative energy generation, or other technologies in energy cooperatives?

>> Have public policies or government interventions played a role in this? If so, which ones?

>> What delays them the most?

What challenges related to **acceptance** or participation have arisen when introducing new energy technologies in communities?

>> are these challenges related to the social or age profile of the community?

4. Energy

Question

How many energy communities primarily use the following types of **energy generation**?

- Solar (PV)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solar (thermal) - Wind Power - Biomass
<p>Please describe the technology if not listed above (e.g. geothermal, hydropower, waste-to-energy):</p>
<p>Which non-PV technologies would you say are growing the fastest, and which ones still face barriers to wider adoption?</p>
<p>How many energy communities primarily use the following types of energy storage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Battery storage - Thermal storage - Cold storage - Seasonal energy storage
<p>If the technology is not listed above, please briefly describe it (e.g. pumped hydro, compressed air, thermal storage):</p>
<p>Which renewable energy technologies are currently emerging among new energy communities, and which ones do you foresee playing a key role in their evolution?</p>
<p>Are there any recommendations or best practices for introducing new sustainable technologies into existing energy communities?</p>

5. Financing

Question
<p>What range of capital is required by energy communities? Is there a value per member?</p>
<p>How are they mostly financed?</p>

- >> Are the energy communities receiving financial support from **public bodies**?
- >> Which type? (e.g. grant, loan, equity etc.)
 - >> at which level: local, regional, national, European?
 - >> Could you name the entity/ies?
- >> Are the energy communities receiving or have received grant(s) from a **foundation/philanthropic source**?
- >> At which stage of their development? (pre-idea, ideation phase, idea-stage etc.)
- >> from which entity/ies (names)?

Are the energy communities involved in **partnership(s)** with **financial institutions**?

If yes, which one(s) (names) or which types (commercial banks etc.)?

What **innovative financial mechanisms** or funding models have been adopted to support the creation and operation of energy communities (e.g., crowdfunding, green bonds, cooperative investment schemes, community energy financing scheme (CEFS) etc.) and for energy community in which sector (e.g. PV, wind farm etc.)?

Is there anything else you would like to add that hasn't been covered in the previous questions and that you consider important to highlight regarding energy communities in your region/country?

Annex B: EC Umbrella entities

The entities that responded to the questions in Annex A were as follows:

EC Umbrella entities in Europe, Poland, Germany and Spain		
Name	Type of entity	Scope
European federation of energy communities (RESCOOP)	Federation	European
Coop Tech Hub	Cooperation Hub	National/Poland
Revision Union of Energy, Development and Digital Cooperatives SERC	Revision Union	National/Poland
Bundesgeschäftsstelle Energiegenossenschaften	Association	National/Germany
Fundación Ecología y Desarrollo (ECODES)	Foundation	National/Spain
Som Comunitats	Cooperative (of energy communities)	Catalonia Region /Spain
Universidad de Mondragón	University	Basq Country Region/Spain
Junta Andaluza de la Energía	Energy Agency	Andalusia Region/Spain
OTC Emececuadrado	Private company	Badajoz Region/Spain